

**TENSILE BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-DIRECTIONAL
GLASS/CARBON HYBRID LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

Tensile tests were carried out on hybrid glass/carbon/epoxy $0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates. It was found that, in general, stiffness and strength decreased as the amount of glass in the laminate increased. The opposite was true for the strain to failure. A step-by-step computational analysis closely modelled the non-linear stress-strain behaviour of the laminates. The Tsai-Hill failure criterion, together with thermal stress calculations, delivered satisfactory results for the tensile strength.

INTRODUCTION

Composites containing more than one type of fibre are commonly known as "hybrid composites". Extensive research has been carried out in the past [1] on uni-directional hybrid materials, but practical requirements call for additional work on multi-directional configurations. The main reason for using hybrid composites in a particular structure lies in the ability to mix the two or more types of fibre in a way so as to "tailor" the material to the exact needs of the structural application. Advantages found with one type of fibre can be used to complement the poor performance of the other type for a particular property. For example, the impact performance of carbon fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRP) can be improved by hybridisation with glass fibre-reinforced plastic (GFRP).

The present paper describes experimental and computational research work carried out on hybrid glass/carbon multi-directional laminates. This

work formed part of an extensive study of uni- and multi-directional glass/carbon hybrid laminates tested in tension, compression and flexure [4]. The main aim of the multi-directional test phase was to establish the extent to which the results of a uni-directional test programme can be used to predict the behaviour of hybrid multi-directional laminates.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Multi-directional hybrid composites were fabricated by laminating pre-impregnated sheets of either XAS carbon or E-glass fibres in Ciba-Geigy 913 epoxy resin. 16-ply symmetric laminates (ply thickness 0.125mm) were produced in three orientation stacking sequences which originated from a basic $0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ$ lay-up (Table 1). For each orientation stacking sequence, a number of material stacking sequences was chosen such that the effects of carbon/glass content, position and orientation could be studied. Within each group, the hybrid stacking sequences spanned the range of the expected direct and shear stiffness and strength values. In particular, the effect of gradually replacing the off-axis carbon layers with glass (at the same orientation) was investigated.

The tensile specimen employed was 200mm long, 20mm wide and 2mm thick. It was fitted with GFRP endplates, thus reducing the gauge length to 100mm. 12 specimens were tested for each lay-up. The laminates were conditioned dry, at room temperature and over silica gel crystals for a period of approximately four months. Both displacement-controlled (hard) and load-controlled (soft) loading conditions were employed.

RESULTS

The failure mode of the various specimens was satisfactory, being predominantly central. Macroscopic examination revealed a large degree of delamination, splitting parallel to the fibres in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° directions, and cracking of the 0° fibres. Typical failed specimens are shown in Figure 1, where it can be seen that damage is in general fairly localised. It should be noted that in both displacement-controlled and load-controlled tests the failure modes were largely similar, and that ultimate failure occurred in a catastrophic fashion, unlike the behaviour of glass-rich uni-directional laminates, for which failure occurs progressively under displacement-controlled loading [2].

TABLE 1
Stacking sequence configurations. c=carbon, g=glass.

Number	Stacking sequence
	$[+45/ 90/-45/ 0 /+45/ 90/-45/ 0]_S$
1	c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c
2	g - g - g - c - c - g - c - c
3	g - g - g - c - g - g - g - c
4	g - g - g - c - g - g - g - g
5	c - g - c - g - c - g - c - g
6	g - g - g - g - g - g - g - g
	$[+45/ 90/-45/ 0 / 0 / 90/ 0 / 0]_S$
7	c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c
8	g - g - g - c - c - g - c - c
9	g - g - g - c - c - g - g - g
10	c - g - c - g - g - g - g - g
11	g - g - g - g - g - g - g - g
	$[+45/ 0 /-45/ 90/+45/ 90/-45/ 0]_S$
12	c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c - c
13	g - c - g - g - c - g - c - c
14	g - g - g - g - g - g - g - g

Figure 1. Typical failed specimens. Top to bottom, stacking sequences 1-6.

Specimens from stacking sequences 1, 2, 5 and 6 were sectioned in the vicinity of the failure, and were examined under a microscope, both along and across the direction of loading. It was found that very little damage had occurred away from the main failure site. Around the main crack there was extensive resin cracking in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° layers, but there was no evidence of such damage covering the entire gauge length. Furthermore, a large amount of delamination was seen with the all-glass specimen.

The experimental tensile results are included in Table 2. The various observations that can be drawn on these results are:

(a) the failure strains of the multi-directional laminates were, in general, very similar to the failure strains of uni-directional material for either carbon or glass [2];

(b) the stacking sequences with 0° carbon layers were about twice as strong and two or three times as stiff as those with 0° glass layers. Therefore, it pays to use a small amount of carbon in order to strengthen and to stiffen a glass laminate;

(c) the replacement of the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of carbon by glass, at the same orientation, resulted in a small decrease in strength and stiffness;

(d) the replacement of the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of glass by carbon, at the same orientation, resulted in a small increase in strength and stiffness, while the shear stiffness was undoubtedly increased as well;

(e) in view of the properties of CFRP and GFRP, it is not surprising that strength and stiffness decreased with decreasing carbon content whilst ultimate strain increased. But this was observed even when the 0° plies remained of carbon, and it is believed that thermal stresses and mechanical coupling contributed to these effects. The degree to which these can be predicted quantitatively will be analysed in the following section;

(f) the interchange of the outer 0° and 90° layers had no effect on the tensile properties; and

(g) the load-controlled tests carried out on stacking sequences 7, 10 and 11 showed a small increase in strength for the glass-rich laminates (as compared with hard loading). This is in agreement with uni-directional test results, where an increase of roughly 10% was observed. The fact that the increase in strength was found to be smaller for multi-directional test pieces suggests that this effect must be 0° -ply-dominated.

Averaged stress-strain curves for some of the displacement-controlled

TABLE 2

Experimental and computational results. HL=Hard, SL=Soft loading.
Secant modulus measured at 0.25% strain. Standard deviation roughly +/-6%.

Stack. seq.	Ultimate stress,HL (MPa)	Ultimate stress,SL (MPa)	Ultimate strain,HL (%)	Axial modulus (GPa)	Percent difference of theory from experiment:		
					ult.stress	ult.strain	modulus
1	778		1.36	56.5	-1.3	+1.5	-1.1
2	722		1.41	54.4	-3.0	+0.7	-8.1
3	716		1.48	49.4	-5.0	-2.0	-4.3
4	485		1.46	36.2	-0.4	0	-3.0
5	479		2.28	26.8	+0.8	-5.3	+1.5
6	404		2.40	23.1	+2.5	-5.0	-2.2
7	1270	1261	1.42	81.5	-6.5	-5.6	+3.9
8	1184		1.38	83.7	-4.2	-0.7	-5.1
9	843		1.50	58.6	-8.9	-7.3	-6.7
10	637	660	2.18	33.9	+3.6	0	-2.4
11	584	599	2.26	30.8	+0.2	-4.4	-2.6
12	788		1.39	56.2	-2.5	-0.7	-0.5
13	724		1.44	51.8	-3.3	-1.4	-3.5
14	409		2.37	23.8	+1.2	-3.8	-5.0

tensile tests are presented in Figure 2. It was found that the stiffness of the multi-directional laminates can either increase or decrease with increasing load. This comes as a result of the combination of two effects, (a) the increase in modulus of the 0° plies as has already been seen with

Figure 2. Experimental stress-strain curves. Lay-up details in Table 1.

uni-directional material [2]; and (b) the decrease in axial modulus of the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, as confirmed in separate tests of $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates. Naturally, there is interaction between the various plies, but whether the stiffness will increase or decrease with load depends mainly on the relative proportion of 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies, and partly on whether these layers are of glass or of carbon.

DISCUSSION

For the computational modelling of the tensile behaviour of the multi-directional stacking sequences the effects of resin cracking, thermal stresses and mechanical interaction between layers were suspected to be important, and therefore have been investigated. In particular, it has been found necessary to include non-linear stiffness effects in the analysis, thus complicating the modelling considerably.

The theoretical investigation is limited to the results obtained with the displacement-controlled tests, which constituted the bulk of the work. The method that was adopted for the solution of the non-linear stress-strain behaviour of the multi-directional laminates was that of simple incremental loading, assuming linear stiffness behaviour over each load increment, and using the updated local strain values to calculate the tangent laminate stiffness. Laminate theory was used for each load step. The method is subject to cumulative error unless a reasonably small load increment is used, and therefore the increment employed here was typically 1 to 4% of the ultimate value.

Values for the basic stiffness properties of uni-directional carbon and glass in tension or compression, and their variation with strain were investigated in previous work [3,4]. In general, these properties were not constant with strain, although large changes were only observed for the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} . Values for the stiffness properties, obtained near zero strain, can be found in Table 3, while more details are available in Reference 4.

The thermal stresses generated in the multi-directional laminates due to the curing procedure were calculated at the start of the incremental stress-strain calculations. The thermal stresses generated were found to be small (as compared to strength) in the fibre direction, but were often large across the fibres. As layers of carbon were replaced by layers of glass at the same orientation, the negative thermal stress σ_1 in the axial

TABLE 3
Stiffness and strength properties used in the computational analysis

	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	S_1 (MPa)	S_2 (MPa)	S_{12} (MPa)
CFRP	144.3	11.04	5.79	0.313	-1500,+2185	-180,+60	80
GFRP	45.6	10.73	5.14	0.274	-1450,+1000	-270,+90	80

layers became larger, thus indicating a possible enhancement of the tensile strain at failure. The opposite behaviour was found for the stresses in the axial glass plies, ie when glass layers were replaced by carbon layers at the same orientation.

Because it was believed to work reasonably well for the stress states investigated here, it was decided to use the Tsai-Hill failure criterion for strength predictions. The data required for this criterion are the tensile and compressive strength values in the longitudinal and transverse directions, as well as the shear strength. These values were obtained experimentally, except for the transverse compressive strength Y_C , which has been shown [5-8] to be equal to between 1 and (at least) 4 times the equivalent value in tension, depending mainly on the loading boundary conditions. In the present calculations, this quantity (Y_C) was varied so that sensitivity to its effects on the tensile strength could be studied for a multi-directional, single-phase, stacking sequence. It was found that as the transverse compressive strength of the material was increased, so did the predicted axial tensile strength of the laminate. This increase however became negligible when Y_C was bigger than roughly three times the transverse tensile strength. Therefore, it was this value that was chosen for the subsequent analysis. The strength data used are included in Table 3.

As predicted by the theoretical model, the various plies in any particular stacking sequence did not fail simultaneously. Typically, the 90° layers failed first, then the $\pm 45^\circ$'s and finally the 0° 's. During a test, once microcracks form in a particular lamina, its stiffness contribution to the laminate is undoubtedly reduced. However, the exact amount of reduction cannot be determined experimentally because of other non-linear effects taking place simultaneously. In particular, the most common source of stiffness reduction arises from resin cracking in the 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ layers. Such cracking is not instantaneous but is instead

spread-out over a range of strain levels. In the present model, the behaviour of these layers (90° and $\pm 45^\circ$) was assumed to be bi-linear, ie linear until ply failure, then linear again but with the transverse and shear stiffnesses reduced by a certain common factor. This factor was derived by fitting theoretical to experimental tensile stiffness results, for either all-carbon or all-glass stacking sequences. For CFRP, a reduction of 50% to the stiffness was adopted, while for GFRP this value was as high as 90%. It was assumed that identical reduction factors applied in tension and compression. In similar work by other researchers [7,9] the magnitude of the stiffness reduction factor ranged between 0 and 100%, the best results obtained near the latter extreme. Furthermore, in Ref.7, upon lamina failure the stress-strain calculation was re-started from the origin, using the updated stiffness values (note that axial stiffness was also reduced). Thus, a drop in the stress was found whenever a particular layer failed. In the present work, this technique was only adopted if a 0° ply failed, because it was believed that the behaviour of the 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies would be pseudo-plastic.

In Table 2 the experimental and theoretical values for σ_{ult} , ϵ_{ult} and E_x (initial) are compared. It can be seen that the agreement between theory and experiment is satisfactory. Furthermore, typical experimental and theoretical stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 3, where it can

Figure 3. Stress-strain curves. Comparison between theory and experiment.

Figure 4. Tangent axial stiffness vs. strain. Theory and experiment.

be seen that the theoretical prediction closely follows the non-linear behaviour of the laminates. This comparison is made clearer when the tangent modulus is plotted against strain (Figure 4). The discontinuities in the theoretical results arise from the stiffness reduction applied when ply failure occurs. In the tests, stiffness reduction occurs slowly over a range of strain loading, and hence the experimental curves are continuous.

CONCLUSIONS

16-ply symmetric laminates were produced in three orientation stacking sequences which originated from a basic $0^\circ/\underline{+}45^\circ/90^\circ$ lay-up. The failure mode of the specimens was satisfactory, being predominantly central. In both displacement- and load-controlled tests the failure modes were largely similar, the ultimate failure occurring in a catastrophic fashion. The tensile stiffness of the laminates was found to decrease with increasing amount of glass, irrespective of the orientation of the latter. The tensile strength was also found to decrease with increasing amount of glass, but the opposite was true for the strain at failure. A non-linear step-by-step computational analysis delivered good results for the various

laminates up to the failure strain. Stiffness reduction factors were imposed upon the failure of individual plies, and these were found to be different for carbon than for glass. The ultimate stress and strain were also predicted well by the use of thermal stress calculations and the Tsai-Hill failure criterion in the step-by-step analysis.

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REFERENCES

1. Kretsis, G., A review of the tensile, compressive, flexural and shear properties of hybrid fibre-reinforced plastics. Composites, 18, January 1987, pp.13-23.
2. Kretsis, G., Matthews, F.L., Morton, J. and Davies, G.A.O., Tensile behaviour of unidirectional glass/carbon hybrid laminates. In Fibre Reinforced Composites 1986, paper C47/86, I.Mech.E., University of Liverpool, UK, April 1986.
3. Kretsis, G., Matthews, F.L., Morton, J. and Davies, G.A.O., Basic technology of hybrid composites. Fourth progress report, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College, London, December 1985.
4. Kretsis, G., Matthews, F.L., Morton, J. and Davies, G.A.O., Basic technology of hybrid composites. Final report, Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College, London, January 1987.
5. Collings, T.A., On the bearing strengths of CFRP laminates. Composites, 13, 1982, pp.241-52.
6. Craddock, J.N., Mechanical properties and elastic limits of hybrid laminates. In proceedings, Fifth International Conference on Composite Materials, eds. W.C. Harrigan Jr., J. Strife and A.K. Dhingra, San Diego, 1985, pp.1505-16.
7. Takahashi, K., Ban, K. and Chou, T-W., Non-linear stress-strain behaviour of carbon/glass hybrid composites. In proceedings, Fifth International Conference on Composite Materials, eds. W.C. Harrigan Jr., J. Strife and A.K. Dhingra, San Diego, 1985, pp.1573-89.
8. Kim, R.Y. and Soni, S.R., Suppression of free-edge delamination by hybridization. In proceedings, Fifth International Conference on Composite Materials, eds. W.C. Harrigan Jr., J. Strife and A.K. Dhingra, San Diego, 1985, pp.1557-72.
9. Talreja, R., Transverse cracking and stiffness reduction in composite laminates. J.Comp.Mat., 19, 1985, pp.355-75.